

Application of Laplace Decomposition Method to Solve Boundary Value Problems

S. S. Handibag¹, Y. M. Muley²

¹Department of Mathematics, Mahatma Basweshwar Mahavidyalaya, Latur,(MH) India

²Department of Mathematics, Kai. Rasika Mahavidyalaya, Deoni, Dist. Latur,(MH) India

Abstract

In this paper, Laplace Decomposition Method (LDM) is applied to nonlinear partial differential equations with boundary conditions. Numerical results obtained by using LDM compared with the results obtained by using Adomian decomposition Method (ADM) and Variational iteration method (VIM).

Key words: Laplace decomposition method, Boundary value problems.

Introduction

Liu [3] and He [4] have worked on Boundary value problems, they have concluded that ADM could not always satisfy all its boundary conditions, leading to an error at its boundary conditions. ADM does not yield correct approximation. But A. M. Wazwaz [2] (2000) shows that this conclusion is not correct. A. M. Wazwaz solve the BVP which solved by Liu [3] and He [4] with the help of Taylor expansion and concluded that the by proper investment of ADM, the exact solution can be easily obtained for BVP of closed form solution. However, if exact solution does not exist, then a rapid convergent series solution is always attainable by this method as proved by [1]. But again Bongsoo Jang [5] (2008) by solving two Boundary value problems concluded that ADM is not appropriate

method to find the exact or accurate approximate solution for the complex Dirchlet boundary value problem. Liu [3], He [4] and Bongsoo Jang [5] in their papers promoted VIM and said that VIM is easy to implement without producing complex term, Adomian polynomials.

In this paper we have employed Laplace decomposition method to solve the BVP's. Illustrative examples show that the proposed method gave the exact solution which is same as solution obtained by VIM in [3, 4, 5]. In the next section we have present the framework in a general way so that it may be used in BVP of same type.

LDM for BVP's

In this paper we shall consider the most general BVP

$$\nabla^2 u + Nu + Ru = h(x, y) \quad (1)$$

Subject to the boundary conditions

$$u(0, y) = \alpha_1(y), \quad u_x(0, y) = \alpha_2(y), \quad u(1, y) = \alpha_3(y) \quad (2)$$

$$u(x, 0) = \beta_1(y), \quad u_y(x, 0) = \beta_2(y), \quad u(x, 1) = \beta_3(x) \quad (3)$$

Where

$\alpha_1(y), \alpha_2(y), \alpha_3(y), \beta_1(x), \beta_2(x), \beta_3(x)$ and $h(x, y)$ are assumed real and as many times differentiable as required for $x, y \in [0, 1]$. Also $\nabla^2 = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2}$, Nu is a nonlinear term and Ru is a remaining linear term. Let us write the equation (1) in the

following form,

$$\frac{\partial^2 u(x,y)}{\partial x^2} = h(x,y) - Nu(x,y) - Ru(x,y) - \frac{\partial^2 u(x,y)}{\partial y^2} \quad (4)$$

Here we are going to find the solution of given BVP in x- direction by taking Laplace transform of equations (4) with respect to x, we get

$$\begin{aligned} s^2 u(s,y) - su(0,y) - u_x(0,y) &= L_x[h(x,y) - Nu(x,y) - Ru(x,y) - u_{yy}(x,y)] \\ u(s,y) &= \frac{1}{s} \alpha_1(y) + \frac{1}{s^2} \alpha_2(y) + \frac{1}{s^2} L_x[h(x,y) - Nu(x,y) - Ru(x,y) - u_{yy}(x,y)] \end{aligned}$$

Taking inverse laplace transform of above equation, we get

$$u(x,y) = \alpha_1(y) + x\alpha_2(y) + L_x^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{s} L_x[h(x,y) - Nu(x,y) - Ru(x,y) - u_{yy}(x,y)] \right] \quad (5)$$

We know that LDM decompose the solution $u(x,y)$ by an infinite series of components

$$u(x,y) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} u_n(x,y) \quad (6)$$

and decompose the nonlinear term $Nu(x,y)$ by an infinite series of polynomials

$$Nu(x,y) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} A_n \quad (7)$$

Where A_n are Adomian polynomials [1] depending on the components $u_0, u_1, u_2, u_3, \dots, u_n$. Adomian polynomials are defined by

$$\begin{aligned} A_n(u_0, u_1, u_2, u_3, \dots, u_n) &= \frac{1}{n!} \frac{d^n}{d\lambda^n} \left[N \left(\sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \lambda^i u_i \right) \right]_{\lambda=0} \end{aligned}$$

Substituting the decomposition series (6) and (7) into the both side of (5) gives $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} u_n(x,y) = \alpha_1(y) + x\alpha_2(y) + \left[L_x^{-1} \frac{1}{s^2} L_x[h(x,y) - \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} A_n - R(\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} u_n(x,y)) - \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} u_{nyy}(x,y)] \right]$

Comparing the both sides of above equation, we get the following recurrence relation

$$u_0(x,y) = \alpha_1(y) + x\alpha_2(y) + L_x^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{s^2} L_x[h(x,y)] \right] \quad (8)$$

$$u_{n+1}(x,y) = -L_x^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{s^2} L_x[A_n + Ru_n(x,y) + u_{nyy}(x,y)] \right], n \geq 0 \quad (9)$$

Once the components $u_n(x,t)$ are determined by the above recursion, the exact or approximate solution $u(x,t)$ in a series form is immediately obtained.

Numerical illustrations

Example 1.

Consider the BVP

$$\nabla^2 u + \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)^2 = 2y + x^4, 0 < x, y < 1 \quad (1.1)$$

Subject to the boundary conditions

$$u(0,y) = 0, \quad u_x(0,y) = a, \quad u(1,y) = y + a \quad (1.2)$$

$$u(x,0) = ax, \quad u_y(x,0) = x^2, \quad u(x,1) = x(x+a) \quad (1.3)$$

Where a is constant, by comparing the above problem with the most general BVP

(1). We get $Nu = \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)^2$, is a nonlinear

term and $h(x, y) = 2y + x^4$, is a source term and the linear term in this problem is zero.

By the LDM for BVP explained in Section 2, we get the following recurrence relation

$$u_0(x, y) = ax + yx^2 + \frac{1}{30} x^6 \quad (1.4)$$

$$u_{n+1}(x, y) = -L_x^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{s^2} L_x [A_n + u_{nyy}(x, y)] \right], n \geq 0 \quad (1.5)$$

The first few Adomian polynomials A_n that represent the nonlinear term $\left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x}\right)$ are defined by

$$\begin{aligned} A_0 &= u_{0y}^2, \\ A_1 &= 2u_{0y}u_{1y}, \\ A_2 &= 2u_{0y}u_{2y} + u_{1y}^2 \end{aligned}$$

From the recurrence (1.4) and (1.5) we get,

$$u_0(x, y) = ax + yx^2 + \frac{1}{30} x^6$$

$$\begin{aligned} u_1(x, y) &= -L_x^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{s^2} L_x [A_0 + u_{0yy}(x, y)] \right], \\ &= -L_x^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{s^2} L_x [u_{0y}^2 + u_{0yy}(x, y)] \right] \\ &= -\frac{1}{30} x^6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} u_2(x, y) &= -L_x^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{s^2} L_x [A_1 + u_{1yy}(x, y)] \right], \\ &= -L_x^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{s^2} L_x [2u_{0y}u_{1y} + u_{1yy}(x, y)] \right] \\ &= -L_x^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{s^2} L_x [(x^2)(0) + 0] \right] = 0 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, $u_3 = 0, u_4 = 0 \dots$ and so on. Substitute the values of $u_0, u_1, u_2, u_3, \dots, u_n$ in (6), we get the exact solution of nonlinear BVP (1.1), which satisfies all boundary conditions (1.2) and (1.3).

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, y) &= ax + yx^2 + \frac{1}{30} x^6 - \frac{1}{30} x^6 \\ &= axyx^2 = x(yx + a) \quad (1.6) \end{aligned}$$

Example 2.

Consider the BVP

$$\nabla^2 u - u = 2e^{-y}, \text{ in } (0,1)^2 \quad (2.1)$$

Subject to the boundary conditions

$$u(0, y) = 0, \quad u_x(0, y) = a, \quad u(1, y) = e^{-y} \quad (2.2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, 0) &= x^2, \quad u_y(x, 0) = \\ -x^2, \quad u(x, 1) &= \frac{x^2}{e} \end{aligned} \quad (2.3)$$

In the given BVP Nonlinear term Nu is zero general linear $Ru = -u$, and source term $h(x, y) = 2e^{-y}$.

From the LDM for BVP's explained in Section 2, we get the following recurrence relation with help of equations (8) and (9).

$$\begin{aligned} u_0(x, y) &= L_x^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{s^2} L_x [2e^{-y}] \right] = \\ \frac{x^2}{2} (2e^{-y}) &= e^{-y}x^2 \end{aligned} \quad (2.4)$$

$$u_{n+1}(x, y) = -L_x^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{s^2} L_x [u_n - u_{nyy}] \right], n \geq 0 \quad (2.5)$$

Calculating each component of the decomposition series (6) yield

$$u_0(x, y) = e^{-y}x^2$$

$$u_1(x, y) = -L_x^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{s^2} L_x [u_0 - u_{0yy}] \right],$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= -L_x^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{s^2} L_x [e^{-y} x^2 - e^{-y} x^2] \right] \\
 &= 0
 \end{aligned}$$

From the recurrence relation (2.5), we can easily see that $u_2 = 0, u_3 = 0 \dots$ and by putting these values in (6), we get

$$u(x, y) = x^2 e^{-y} \quad (2.6)$$

Which is the exact solution satisfied all given boundary conditions (2.2), (2.3). It is worth nothing that only in one iteration yield the exact solution.

Conclusion

This article, Laplace decomposition method(LDM) is applied to solve nonlinear partial differential equations with boundary conditions in x direction by taking Laplace transform with respect to x.

The results of two examples are compared with VIM [2, 3, 5]. The results of these two examples tell us that both methods LDM and VIM can be used alternatively for the solution of higher order boundary value problems.

References

[1] G. Adomian, A Review of the Decomposition Method in Applied Mathematics, Journal of Mathematical Analysis and Applications, Vol. 135, No. 2, 501-544, 1988.

[2] A. M. Wazawaz, " A note on using Adomian decomposition method for solving boundary value problems, Foundations of physics Letters, 13(5) 493-498, 2000.

[3] G. L. Liu, " Weighted residual decomposition method in nonlinear applied mathematics," Proceedings, 6 congress of Modern Mathematics and Mechanics (MM M-VI), 643-648, 1995.

[4] J. H. He, "A new approach to nonlinear partial differential equations, Comm. Nonlinear Sci. Numer. Simulation," 2(4), 230 - 240, 1997.

[5] Bongsoo Jang, "Exact solution to the boundary value problems by VIM", Journal of Korean, Vol. 19, No. 4, 1371 - 1377, 2008.

[6] S. S. Handibag and B. D. Karande, Existence the Solutions of Some Fifth-Order Kdv Equation by Laplace Decomposition Method, American Journal of Computational Mathematics, 2013, 3, 80-85 <http://dx.doi.org/10.4236/ajcm.2013.31013> Published Online March 2013.

[7] S. S. Handibag and B. D. Karande, Application of Laplace Decomposition Method to Solve Linear and Nonlinear Heat Equation, International Journal of Applied Physics and Mathematics, Vol. 2, No. 5, September 2012.

[8] A. M. Wazwaz, The Hirota's bilinear method and the tanh-coth method for multiple soliton solutions of the Sawada-Kotera Kadomtsev-Petviashvili equation, App. Math. and Comp., 200 (1): 160-166, 2008.

[9] Borhanifar, A. and M.M. Kabir, New periodic and soliton solutions by application of Exp-function method for nonlinear evolution equations, J. Comp. Applied Math., 229 (1): 158-167, 2009.

[10] Engui Fan and Y.C. Hon, Applications of extended tanh method to special

types of nonlinear equations, Applied
Math. and Comp., 141 (2-3): 351-358,
2003.